

The Effect of Work Motivation, Work Discipline, And Work Environment on Lecturer Performance with Lecturer's Job Satisfaction as a Moderating Variable

Zulhairani¹, Yusuf Ronny Edward²

^{1,2}Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Lecturers are educators at universities who are specially appointed for the purpose of teaching. The main mission of higher education is to develop and establish knowledge through the experience of the three dharmas of higher education. This study aims to determine whether work motivation, work discipline, and work environment affect the performance of lecturers with job satisfaction as a moderating variable at the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University. The data collection method in this study used a questionnaire. This sampling technique data collection using simple random sampling a total sample of 105 from a total population of 143 permanent lecturers at the Faculty of Economics at the University..The results obtained in this study show 1) there is a significant effect between work motivation variables on lecturer performance, 2) there is a significant influence between work discipline variables on lecturer performance, 3) there is no significant effect between work environment variables and lecturer performance, 4) lecturer satisfaction variable is not a moderating variable that can weaken work environment, strengthen work discipline, and work motivation..

KEYWORDS: Motivation, Discipline, Environment, Satisfaction, Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Lecturers are one of the most influential factors in higher education in Indonesia. Duties, roles and responsibilities of lecturers are very important in realizing and improving the quality of human resources of a national higher education. To carry out the duties, roles and responsibilities, competent and professional lecturers are needed in carrying out their duties. In the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers. That "Lecturers are declared as professional educators and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing, and disseminating science, technology, and art through education, research, and community service. In an effort to improve performance which is influenced by many factors, the performance in it cannot be separated from the performance of existing human resources, namely lecturers. The Ministry of National Education (2004) states that lecturer performance is the ability to carry out the work or tasks of the lecturer in completing a job. Performance evaluation must go through a systematic assessment to find out the results of work and performance.

the expected motivation from someone is that the motivation can affect the person's performance. Discipline is also something that must be done by everyone in setting an example for others (Rosida ,2009). This is supported by the theory developed by Rivai (2014) when someone is motivated, he will try his best to achieve goals, but not necessarily high efforts will result in high performance. tall one. Therefore, it takes the intensity and quality of these efforts and is focused on organizational goals. Work discipline is an attitude that is reflected in the actions or behavior of individuals. Work discipline is an important factor that affects the performance of lecturers and will encourage work optimally and efficiently to improve performance in developing the tasks carried out. Discipline is the most important operative function of human resource management, because the better a person's discipline, the higher the person's performance (Hasibuan ,2003).. The environment can also give a sense of comfort if the lecturers get a safe atmosphere, which can make things easier. The environment can also provide a sense of comfort if the lecturers get a safe atmosphere, which can make work easier. the work environment is everything that is around the workers that can affect them in carrying out their duties. -assigned tasks (Sunyoto ,2015).

II. LITERATURE RIEVIEW

Performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, not violating the law and not

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contrary to morals and ethics (Afandi, 2018). A person has the ability to find reasons or impetus to act. Everyone has a desire that is an impetus to act, but often that urge is weakened by external factors. The weakening of this drive can be seen from the loss of hope and helplessness and can affect the performance of lecturers. Work motivation is formed from the attitude of an employee in dealing with work situations. Work motivation is a condition that moves employees who are directed to achieve organizational goals or work goal (Mangkunegara, 2012).

Motivation is the whys of behavior (Hersey and Blanchard, 2008). This implies that only a certain impulse causes someone to behave or act something. Furthermore, he argues that the motivation of people depends on the strength of their motivation. Thus, everyone has the urge to do for himself or maybe also for others. Discipline is one of the realizations of the goals of educational institutions, with the enforcement of good discipline, it will make lecturers and willing to do all the tasks assigned to them in order to achieve optimal performance so that this is in harmony with the partial relationship between work discipline and lecturer performance. The partial relationship between work discipline and employee performance which states that work discipline is an important instrument in supporting lecturer performance (Hasibuan, 2012).

discipline as the use of some form of punishment or sanction if employees deviate. The use of punishment is used when managers are faced with problems of subordinate behavior that are not in accordance with regulations and work performance that is below company standards (Gibson et al, 1996). Discipline is behavior and discipline in accordance with rules and regulations, or behavior obtained from training that is carried out continuously (Gordon, 1996). Everything that is around workers and can affect them in carrying out the tasks assigned (Nitisemito, 1996). The work environment is the entire tooling and materials encountered, the surrounding environment in which a person works. , work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as groups (Sedarmayati, 2001),.

The work environment is something that exists in the workers' environment that can affect themselves in carrying out tasks such as temperature, humidity, ventilation, lighting, noise, cleanliness of the workplace, and whether or not work equipment is adequate (Afandi, 2018). The work environment can be interpreted as the entire tooling faced, the surrounding environment in which a worker, his work methods, as the influence of his work both as individuals and as a group.. explains "Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves his work". Job satisfaction in work is job satisfaction enjoyed in work by obtaining work results, placement, treatment, equipment and a good working environment (Hasibuan ,2013). Satisfaction outside of work is employee job satisfaction that is enjoyed outside of work with the amount of remuneration that will be received from the results of his work, so that he can buy his needs. Job satisfaction is a positive feeling about work, resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics (Robbins and Judge, 2015).

III. METHOD

Population is the total number of units or individuals whose characteristics are to be studied. And these units are called units of analysis, and can be people, institutions, things. (Djarwanto, 1994). In this study, permanent lecturers at the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University, as a population of 143 people. In this study, it was designed with quantitative research. Quantitative research has a special, detailed, and static nature. The flow of quantitative research itself has been planned from the beginning and cannot be changed anymore. quantitative data is data in the form of numbers, or quantitative data that is scored (scoring). So quantitative data is data that has a tendency to be analyzed by means or statistical techniques. The data can be in the form of numbers or scores and is usually obtained using a data collection tool whose answers are in the form of a range of scores or weighted questions (Sugiyono, 2015). The data collection technique used a questionnaire with the help of a google form which was distributed to Permanent Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, Unpri, who were willing to fill out the questionnaire. The moderation test or the Moderated Regression test Analysis (MRA) is a special application of multiple linear regression, where in the regression equation contains an element of interaction, namely the multiplication between two or more independent variables (Ghozali, 2011). The interaction test of this moderating variable aims to knowing the extent to which the interaction of the moderating variables of job satisfaction moderating work motivation, work discipline and work environment on the performance of permanent lecturers

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Regression analysis is structured to see the relationship that is built between the research variables, whether the relationship that is built is positive or negative. Based on the results of data processing that has been done, it can be seen that the relationship model from multiple linear regression analysis can be seen in the table below..

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Table 4.1

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partia l	Part
1 (Constant)	11.203	5.617		1.995	.049			
X1	.235	.082	.233	2.872	.005	.269	.275	.232
X2	.555	.087	.541	6.397	.000	.532	.537	.516
X3	.329	.288	.097	1.143	.256	.087	.113	.092

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on table 4.1, it can be arranged a research model with the following regression equation:

$$Y = 11.203 + 0.235X1 + 0.555X2 + 0.329X3$$

The multiple regression equation model means:

1. The constant value is 11.203 which means that if the independent variables, namely Work Motivation (X1), Work Discipline (X2), Work Environment (X3) are equal to zero, then the performance (Y) is 11.203.
2. The value of the regression coefficient X1 = 0.235 indicates that if work motivation increases by 100%, it will increase the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers by 23.5%. The magnitude of the influence of work motivation on the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers is 6.3% (the result of multiplying the Beta and Zero-order values), which means that the contribution of work motivation to the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers is 6.3% as a result of indicators of work motivation variables (X1) and beyond may be influenced by variables not included in this study. This can be seen from the value of the standardized coefficients in table 4.10.
3. The value of the regression coefficient X2 = 0.555 indicates if work discipline has increased by 100%, it will increase the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers by 55.5%. The magnitude of the effect of work discipline on the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers is 29.5% (the result of multiplying the Beta and Zero-order values), which means that the contribution of work discipline to the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers is 29.5% as a result of work discipline variable indicators (X2) and beyond that may be influenced by variables not included in this study. This can be seen from the value of the standardized coefficients in table 4.10.
4. The value of the regression coefficient X3 = 0.329 indicates that if the work environment increases by 100%, it will increase the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers by 32.9%. The magnitude of the influence of the work environment on the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers is 2.8% (the result of multiplying the Beta and Zero-order values), which means that the contribution of the work environment to the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers is 2.8% as a result of indicators of work environment variables (X3) and beyond that may be influenced by variables not included in this study. This can be seen from the value of the standardized coefficients in table 4.10.

The hypothesis states that work motivation (X1) and work discipline (X2) have a positive and significant effect, but the work environment (X3) has a positive but not significant effect on performance (Y). The following is Table 4.19 of the results of the t-test calculation for each variable.

In the table 4.1 , the t-test statistic is obtained, as follows: a). Work Motivation Variable (X1), with a probability level of 0.005. Thus, it can be concluded that $P = 0.005 < = 0.05$, so accept the hypothesis which states that job satisfaction has a significant effect on performance. b) Work Discipline Variable (X2), with a probability level of 0.000. Thus, it can be concluded that $P = 0.000 < = 0.05$, so accept the hypothesis which states that the leadership style variable has a significant effect on performance. c) Communication variable (X3), with a probability level of 0.256. Thus, it can be concluded that $P = 0.256 > = 0.05$, so reject the hypothesis that the communication variable has a significant effect on performance.

The F statistic test (simultaneous) was conducted to determine whether the independent variables (independent) together had a significant effect or not on the dependent variable (dependent). Simultaneous test results can be seen in table 4.2

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Table 4.2

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	168.091	3	56.030	17.536	.000 ^a
	Residual	322.709	101	3.195		
	Total	490.800	104			

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on table 4.2, it can be seen that there is a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. This shows that work motivation, work discipline and work environment together have a significant effect on the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers.

The Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) test is a special application of multiple linear regression, where the regression equation contains an interaction element, namely the multiplication between two or more independent variables. Can be seen in the table below.

- a. Job Satisfaction is not a moderating variable that can strengthen or weaken the influence of Work Motivation on Lecturer Performance.

Table 4.3

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10.825	2.558		4.231	.000
	X1	.183	.081	.181	2.264	.026
	Z	.408	.060	.547	6.829	.000
2	(Constant)	-33.343	22.749		-1.466	.146
	X1	1.745	.804	1.731	2.171	.032
	Z	2.141	.889	2.866	2.409	.018
	Moderating1	-.061	.031	-2.994	-1.954	.054

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on the results from table 4.3 that the interaction of the multiplication between the work motivation variable (X1) and the moderating variable (Z) shows the results where the equation, namely the moderating variable (Z) is significant, and the multiplication equation between the work motivation variable (X1) and the moderating variable (Z) is not significant, then the variable Z is not a moderator variable, but it is an independent, intervening, exogenous, antecedent, or predictor variable.

- b. Job satisfaction is not a moderating variable that can strengthen or weaken the influence of Work Discipline on Lecturer Performance.

Table 4.4

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10.753	2.221		4.841	.000
	X2	.294	.101	.287	2.914	.004
	Z	.298	.074	.400	4.058	.000

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2	(Constant)	-15.394	22.299		-.690	.492
	X2	1.252	.819	1.222	1.529	.129
	Z	1.340	.887	1.794	1.511	.134
	Moderating2	-.038	.032	-2.104	-1.178	.241

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on the results from table 4. that the interaction of the multiplication between the work discipline variable (X2) variable (Z) shows the results where the equation, namely the moderating variable (Z), is not significant and the multiplication the work discipline variable (X2) and the moderating variable (Z) is not significant, then the variable Z is Homologizer Moderat

- a. Job satisfaction is not a moderating variable that can strengthen or weaken the influence of the Work Environment on Lecturer Performance.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	11.496	5.464		2.104	.038
X3	.204	.274	.060	.745	.458
Z	.428	.060	.573		.000
2 (Constant)	16.468	53.630		.307	.759
X3	-.050	2.748	-.015	-.018	.985
Z	.241	2.003	.323	.120	.904
Moderating3	.010	.103	.264	.093	.926

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on the results from table 4. that the interaction of the multiplication between the work environment variable (X3) and the moderating variable (Z) shows the results where the equation, namely the moderating variable (Z), is not significant and the multiplication equation between the work environment variable (X3) and the moderating variable (Z) is not significant, then the variable Z is Homologizer Moderator.

Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that work motivation has a significant influence on the performance of lecturers at the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University. This means that work motivation is one of the important factors that can affect the performance of lecturers. Mutually motivating relationship is an encouragement within the lecturer to carry out an activity or task of education and teaching, research, and community service as well as possible in order to be able to achieve work performance (performance) optimally. Lecturers will be able to achieve maximum performance if they have high work motivation. The work motivation that lecturers need to have must be grown from within themselves apart from the work environment. Work discipline is a tool used by managers to change a behavior as well as an effort to increase one's awareness and willingness to obey all agency regulations and applicable social norms (Harttik ,2014),. From the results of the study it can be seen that work discipline have an influence on the performance of lecturers. If the lecturer is not disciplined in working, the results obtained will not be optimal. The impact of indiscipline in work is not only detrimental to the institution but also reflects the quality of the human resources of the institution concerned. The work environment does not have a significant (not significant) effect on the performance of lecturers at the permanent lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, University of Prima Indonesia. This can be seen from the lack of comfort during learning activities which can be caused by

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inadequate facilities in the classroom such as the room feels hot when teaching (Arianto, 2013). Based on the results of the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) test, it is found that job satisfaction as a moderating variable does not directly affect work motivation on lecturer performance. This is because the lecturers are satisfied with the results obtained. So that lecturers with satisfaction motivation have less effect on lecturer performance. From the results obtained that job satisfaction is an independent variable.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research and discussions conducted by researchers regarding the influence of competence, training and motivation on the performance of UNPRI permanent lecturers, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Work motivation has a significant effect on the performance of lecturers at the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University. This means that the higher the work motivation, the higher the lecturer's performance.
2. Work discipline has a significant effect on the performance of lecturers at the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University. This means that the higher the work discipline, the higher the lecturer's performance.
3. The work environment has no significant effect on the performance of the lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University.
4. Work motivation, work discipline, and work environment simultaneously affect the performance of lecturers.
5. Job satisfaction is not a moderating variable that can strengthen/weaken the influence of work motivation on the performance of lecturers at the Faculty of Economics, University of Prima Indonesia.
6. Job satisfaction is not a moderating variable that can strengthen/weak the influence of work discipline on the performance of lecturers at the Faculty of Economics, University of Prima Indonesia.
7. Job satisfaction is not a moderating variable that can strengthen/weaken the influence of the work environment on the performance of lecturers at the Faculty of Economics, University of Prima Indonesia.

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